

IMPLEMENTATION OF TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL CODE OF CONDUCT AS VERITABLE TOOL FOR TACKLING MENACE OF CORRUPTION IN NIGERIAN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Cite (APA): Shittu T. O., Agbola B. A. & Mohammed M. O. (2024). Implementation of Teacher's Professional Code of Conduct As Veritable Tool for Tackling Menace of Corruption in Nigerian Secondary Schools. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Nigerian Economy* 4(1)

Abstract

This study explores the implementation of a teacher's professional code of conduct as a veritable tool for tackling the menace of corruption in Nigeria secondary schools. A teacher's professional code of conduct is an essential tool necessary to fight against corrupt practices among teachers in the school. The code of conduct provides basis for disciplinary actions against erring teachers who engage in corrupt activities and ensuring that the secondary education system remains free of corruption in Nigeria. The key challenges and causes of corruption orchestrated by teachers in Nigerian secondary schools includes: embezzlement of funds, indiscipline, selling of school properties without approval, bribery, engaging in examination dishonesty, extortion of money from students, exchanging sex for grade syndrome, poor remuneration package and unbefitting conditions of service. By implementing clear ethical standards and responsibilities, the code of conduct will promote integrity, transparency, accountability, and professional behaviour among teachers. In conclusion, the study asserted that enforcing a robust professional code of conduct can mitigate the menace of corruption among professional teachers and embrace academic excellence in the Nigerian secondary school system. Therefore, the study recommended among others that the government should implement a special salary scale for teachers improve their welfare package and conditions of service as a veritable tool to curb teacher's embezzlement of funds, bribery, examination malpractices, sex for grade syndrome eroding some public secondary school in Nigeria and provide professional code of conduct training for teacher to fostering academic integrity and excellence in the school system.

Keywords: Code of Conduct, Corruption, Implementation, Teacher and Teaching Profession

Introduction

All over the world, code of conduct seems to be a set of rules, principles, and guidelines that outline expected behaviour and ethical standards for individuals or organizations. However, teacher's professional code of conduct is a set of principles, guidelines, and standards that outline expected behavior and ethical practices for teachers in their professional roles. It provides a framework for teachers to maintain the highest standards of integrity, professionalism, and responsibility.

However, the teacher's professional ethics incorporates respect for students, colleagues, and parents, maintaining confidentiality and privacy, promoting inclusive and diverse learning environments, avoiding conflicts of interest and harassment, upholding academic integrity and honesty, maintaining professional boundaries, continuing professional development, reporting concerns and allegations (TRCN, 2004). Perhaps, the consequences of non-compliance to the stipulated code of conduct by teachers in secondary school disciplinary action on withdrawal of licensure and certification; loss of professional reputation; civil and criminal liability; termination of appointment; and regulatory penalties (fines, sanctions).

Today, corruption seems to be a global phenomenon that affects public and private secondary schools in Nigeria. Corruption seems to be a global pandemic that affects socio-economic, political and education sector. The secondary education in Nigeria is to help individuals live a useful life in society as well as prepare them for higher education. A major challenge to secondary education in Nigeria is corruption. The perception of corruption especially in private schools is very high and uncontrollable (Nwankwo & Nweke, 2016). In Nigeria, the most pressing case of educational corruption started in 1906 when essential school exams were leaked (Asiyai, 2020). Since then, corruption has resurfaced and spread like disease in the secondary education systems. It has been observed that corrupt practices among professional teachers involve accepting bribes for grades or academic favours from students, teachers involved in admission scandals, examination malpractices, embezzlement of school funds and stealing of school properties due to poor salary and arrears. These challenges have made teaching not to be respected as a profession like every other discipline such as: Nursing, medicine, law, accounting, engineer, architect and so on. Corruption as an ethical and social problem which varies from one private school to another, ministry to ministry, place to place, time to time, culture to culture, and with the level of economic development (Aluko in Nwankwo & Nweke, 2016).

In the secondary school system, corruption within the teaching profession cannot be underrated because the state of teacher recruitment process, appointment, discipline, transfer and promotion practices today observes to be faulty and unprofessional which contribute to poor quality teacher and student failure. As a result, the future of teaching profession may face several challenges if not properly address. Kumah et al., (2023) posited that most instructors being produced by the

Teaching Service Commission are engrossed with a poor attitude toward indiscipline among college students. Such attitudes like sexual harassment and receiving bribes of every type from the students, can promote indiscipline. However, inadequate commitment to obligation by teachers, incessant industrial moves, insufficient incentives, and a body of workers' welfare rules are additional factors that promote corrupt practices in Lagos State secondary schools (Shaibu, 2024).

Menace of Corruption in the Secondary Education Sector

Corruption seems to be a common disease which erodes the public and private secondary school system with notable stakeholders including teachers, principals, supervisors, invigilators, proprietors, policymakers, the examination councils and above all, leads to the abuse of teaching as a profession like other professional bodies in Nigeria. According to Suleiman et al. (2019), came up with a clear definition of corruption as the use of public places for private advantage. Public secondary schools are also involved in corruption when a principal or teacher accepts, solicits, or extorts a bribe from the students or parents (Nwankwo & Nweke, 2016). It is also abused when private secondary school proprietors or teachers actively offer bribes to circumvent education policies and processes for competitive advantage and profit. Moreover, some parents also intend to send their children to private schools primarily to enable their children obtain excellent results and on the other hand support examination malpractices which have in turn degraded the quality and standard of education in Nigeria.

The menace of corruption in secondary schools can have severe consequences on the education system and society. It has been observed that some element of corruption practices orchestrated by teachers in public and private secondary schools in Nigeria includes siphoning of school instructional material and other teaching aids to the black market especially the science teachers, principals and bursars; collecting of money for continuous assessment and inter-exams grades; collecting money for change of grade or producing fake result; selling admissions without entrance examinations (especially in higher institutions); creating the necessity for private lesson to the student and charging compulsory fees; and teachers' persistent absenteeism to accommodate other income outside their normal assigned duties. These are some observed elements of corruption practices in secondary schools:

1. **Teachers – Students Corruption:** This involves underpaid teacher who make ends meet and charges students a “paper fee” in order for them to take the end of year national examination for their grade. However, some students used money to influence their teachers, invigilators or supervisor. Some teachers encourage cheating, plagiarism, grade inflation or manipulation, issuance of fake diplomas or certificates.
2. **Sexual Corruption:** This involves some female students who used sex to influence their school teachers, principals or proprietors to enable them to have access to expo-materials in the hall or using hired machinery that will assist them with a duplicate of their documents with money.
3. **Institutional and Administrative Corruption:** This involves principal embezzlement of funds, encouraging nepotism, favoritism, fraud, student admissions scandal, manipulation of teachers’ promotions and school accreditation scams.
4. **Security Officer/Gatekeeper Corruption:** This exists among uniform officers who, when assigned, attached, or posted to such schools or centers for official monitoring and investigation, may reverse such assignment as a means of harassing the school or the students to settle them or arrest them for examination malpractices.
5. **Examination Corruption:** This involves both the invigilators, supervisors, syndicates or examination officers especially during the external examinations ganging up with the proprietors to mobilize the students raise some fund for their transportations so as to allocate them what they refer as extra-time.
6. **Admission Corruption:** This involves admission scandals e.g., bribery, favoritism). In a similar study by Okpechi et al. (2018), corruption includes fraud; they interpreted the terms of these numbers as follows.
 - I. **Embezzlement:** This includes the theft of public resources by public officials. An example in education would be the use of PTA funds for school improvements or the construction of a secondary school library.
 - II. **Bribery:** This includes payment (in cash or in-kind) given or received to act as a teacher in a relationship or where a person is not eligible to participate in the job but has worked as a teacher;
 - III. **Fraud:** This refers to a commercial crime that involves some form of deception, fraud, or deception. One of the consequences of this in education is the creation of additional credit or the issuance of certificates by school owners or administrators.

- IV. **Extortion:** Obtaining money or other resources through the use of force, violence, or the threat of force. There may be fewer instances of violence or the threat of violence in education than in other professions. However, there are cases where teachers commit sexual offenses against students or require parents to pay illegal or unauthorized fees to enroll their children.
- V. **Nepotism:** This is associated with the abuse of power that implies “privatization” and the sale of school resources or equipment. This includes cases of nepotism where public officials favor their family or friends. There are many examples of people showing interest in learning, including recruitment based on peer groups, organisations, or family friends.

Causes of Corruption Among Teachers in Secondary School

According to Ayobami in Shaibu (2024), causes of corruption among teachers in secondary school consist of the following:

1. Poverty: This can impact specifically when teachers are poorly paid to assertive promotion or were prompted. This may additionally arise due to exploitation from the primary to the students through sorting to upgrade their non-stop assessment (CA) to get better grades in the course of or before the exam.
2. Employment: Employment may cause a scenario where an applicant may find it hard to find a teaching job in his career and ultimately discover himself in a coaching subject that might not be his fundamental career due to unemployment in the labour market.
3. Low-salary of Teachers: Teachers’ salaries observed to be low and a group of teacher can be forced to use their respectable positions to collect bribes to cater for their immediate need.

Implementation of Teachers Code of Conduct in Secondary School

Precisely, teaching is noble profession and teachers must operate within the established rules and regulations. These set of regulations are prescribed in form of ethics. These code of ethics in the teaching profession in Nigeria is fashioned after the UNESCO/ILO recommended codes of conduct (TRCN, 2004). They are the reflection of the values of the teachers and their profession.

The ethics demand as follow:

1. Teaching profession should be standardized and teachers must have undertaken some approved courses appropriate for teacher preparation before being employed.

2. Teachers should be disciplined and Teachers Disciplinary Committee should perform their duty when necessary.
3. Teachers should enjoy academic freedom particularly in - deciding what to teach, materials to use and the appropriate methodology.
4. Teachers assessment should be objectively done and there should be right of appeal against such assessment.
5. The relationship among teacher and between teachers and parents should be that of mutual cooperation.
6. Teachers should strive to ensure high professionals standards.
7. Teachers should take active part in extra-curricular activities for the benefit of their pupils.
8. Teachers should maintain cordiality with administrative and other staffers in the schools for good working relationship.
9. Teachers should participate in social and public life of the community in the interest of teacher's personal development and for them to be socially relevant.
10. Teachers should also be free to exercise their civic rights and be eligible for public office.
11. Teachers should not show any form of discrimination in their operation in or out of school.
12. Teachers should not engage in any form of defamation of colleagues.
13. It is unethical for a teacher to engage in touting or using dubious means such as deception or misinformation to take away clients and learners from colleagues.
14. Teacher should respect child's right and dignity without any
15. Prejudice to sex, race colour, creed or religion.
16. The teachers should also ensure confidentiality of personal information and other records of the learner disclosed to him.
17. The teachers should have a right to fair remuneration but should avoid over-pricing of services.
18. It is against the ethics of the teaching profession to sexually harass a learner.
19. Teachers should not be involved in any form of examination malpractices.
20. It is against the ethics of teaching for teacher to engage in cultism, bribery and corruption.
21. It is unethical for a teacher to give corporal punishment unless duly authorized to do so.
22. Teachers are also barred from influencing the learners ideologically.
23. It is ethical for teachers to respect contractual obligations and the rule of law.

It is therefore note that, the sting of corruption in secondary education in Nigeria is biting very hard and has to be checked before it goes out of hand through the administration of the established code of conduct for teachers.

Implications

Implementing the teachers' professional code of conduct to curb corrupt practices in secondary schools helps to enhances professional reputation, build trust with students, parents, and colleagues, supports student learning and well-being, promote accountability, transparency and responsibility, fosters a positive school culture. The causes of corruption orchestrated by teachers in Nigerian secondary school includes embezzlement of fund, indiscipline, selling of school properties without approval, bribery, engaged in examination dishonest, extortion of money from students, exchanging sex for grade syndrome, poor remuneration package and unbecoming conditions of service. It is therefore, observed that perceived corrupt practices among professional teacher are responsible for the destruction of social welfare and the decline in secondary educational standards in Lagos State, Nigeria. This position is in line with Chinyere and Chukwuma (2017), who found that extortion, cheating in examinations, and bribery by teachers are forms of corruption. It is therefore necessary for secondary school administrator to implement teacher professional code of conduct as stipulated by Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN).

Conclusion

Corruption is a violation of established rules and regulations of formal organisation for personal interest. Corrupt practices among professional teachers in Nigerian secondary education take many forms, including falsification of official documents, sexual harassment, stealing and extortion of money from students, bribery for admission to public schools, and favoritism in recognition. The study concluded that implementing code of conduct in secondary school would help to improve teacher conduct, enhanced student learning, increased parent trust, positive school culture, professional development opportunities. However, enforcing a robust professional code of conduct can mitigating the menace of corruption among professional teachers and embrace academic excellence in Nigerian secondary school system.

Recommendations

The study recommended the following among others that:

1. Government should genuinely implement special salary scale for teachers to improve their welfare and conditions of service as a veritable tool to curb the menace of corrupt in secondary school system.
2. Authority of public secondary schools should create awareness to eliminate corrupt practices and encourage teachers to integrate code values into teaching practices, and demonstrate professional conduct in classroom
3. Governments through ministry of Education should review the teachers' professional programs and provide periodic workshops training on code of conduct expectations.
4. Administrator of public secondary schools should implement code of conduct into school policies, teacher evaluations, and student handbooks.
5. Government should provide financial resources for teachers to maintain professional development.
6. Codes of conduct should be implemented by the teachers' organizations, since such codes greatly contribute to ensuring the prestige of the profession and the exercise of professional duties in accordance with agreed principles.
7. Public secondary school principals should establish anti-corruption clubs in schools as a way of creating awareness for students and staff the dangers of corruption.
8. Principals should encourage debates and essay writings on corruption related topics in school in order to sensitize staff and students about corruption and the evils associated with it.

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